

The impact of creatine supplementation on renal function: A case report and literature review

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Abstract

Creatine supplementation is one of the most widely used dietary supplements worldwide, yet its potential adverse effects on kidney function remain a concern. We report a case of a 25-year-old man who presented with symptoms of left renal colic and exhibited a temporary elevation in serum creatinine levels following oral intake of 10 grams of creatine. Laboratory tests showed elevated serum creatinine (2.12 mg/dL) and urea (45 mg/dL), with an estimated creatinine clearance of 60.3 ml/min. After analgesic and antispastic treatment, the patient's symptoms resolved, and subsequent follow-up indicated normalization of renal function parameters. While several longitudinal, controlled studies on the adverse effects of exogenous creatine supplementation have been published, no evidence of kidney function deterioration has been observed in healthy subjects. Creatine supplementation can alter serum creatinine levels, potentially serving as a false indicator of kidney injury. In this case, we believe the observed increase in creatinine levels was a transient effect of exogenous creatine intake without any actual impairment of renal function.

Take-home message: While creatine supplementation is generally safe and does not typically alter renal function markers in healthy individuals, it may cause renal "stress" in predisposed subjects. Caution and monitoring are advised, especially for those with existing kidney conditions.

Keywords: Adverse effects; creatine; dietary supplements; kidney disease; renal function.

INTRODUCTION

Creatine supplementation is an effective way to increase sports performance and is one of the most commonly used dietary supplements worldwide [1,2]. The kidney plays an important role in body homeostasis, metabolizing and excreting

exogenous compounds such as creatine. Specifically, concerns and questions about renal function began to appear after British nephrologists Pritchard and Kalra published a study reporting significant renal function loss in subjects who used 2 g of creatine per day for 14 days [3].

We report a case of a young man who showed a transitory elevation of serum levels of creatininemia following an oral creatine intake.

CASE DESCRIPTION

A 25-year-old man presented to the Emergency room with symptoms suggestive of left renal colic. He had no other illness or previous similar episode. On physical examination, objective parameters were normal. His abdomen was treatable, painful on the left side with weakly positive Giordano's sign.

Laboratory tests showed: hemoglobin 15.2 g/dL; red blood cells 4,750,000/mm³; hematocrit 44%; white blood cells 9,200/mm³; serum creatinine 2.12 mg/dL; serum urea 45 mg/dL; Na 143 mEq/L; K 4.03 mEq/L; urine dipstick showed: pH 5 and presence of hemoglobin. The estimated creatine clearance by the Cockcroft-Gault equation was 60.3 ml/min.

The patient subsequently reported having taken orally 10 g of creatine two days earlier for reintegrative purposes after intense physical activity. After analgesic and antispastic treatment, the patient was discharged with the resolution of the symptoms. The following control highlighted a complete normalization of the serum parameters of the renal function.

DISCUSSION

The trivial case of renal colic in itself posed a problem of differential diagnosis relating to the finding of increased creatininemia associated with dietary intake of creatine. Exogenous creatine supplements are often consumed by athletes up to 20 g/day for a few days, followed by 1 to 10 g/day for weeks, months, and even years. Creatine can also improve some clinical symptoms in rheumatic diseases [4,5], metabolic disturbances [6], myopathies [7], neurodegenerative diseases [8], chronic obstructive pulmonary disease [9], and congestive heart failure [10]; recently, creatine showed as an adjuvant for tackling the clinical features in long-COVID [11,12].

Usually, consumers do not report any adverse effects, but it increases muscle mass. Some reports show that creatine supplementation protects heart, muscle, and neurological diseases [13]. Gastrointestinal disorders and muscle cramps have occasionally been reported in healthy individuals [13,14]. Nonetheless, the potential effects of creatine, particularly on kidneys, are still a matter of debate [15].

In 1998, Pritchard and Kalra [3] described the first renal damage induced by creatine supplementation. This was a patient with known focal segmental glomerulosclerosis with normal renal function who, following temporary intake of creatine, showed an increase in creatininemia and worsening of glomerular filtration data, which regressed with normalization of the parameters following suspension of intake of the substance.

Another case published by Koshy et al. [16], reported the onset of transient acute renal failure with biopsy evidence of interstitial nephritis in a subject who was taking oral creatine supplement. Remote observation of the patient allowed us to verify the complete normalization of renal function data.

Other additional anecdotal cases have been reported [17-23]; some of these patients had some concomitant underlying renal diseases (such as tubular damage, focal interstitial nephritis, or acute tubular necrosis), or there was an association with misuse or abusive use of other substances [15].

The literature reports several longitudinal, controlled studies on the adverse effects of exogenous creatine supplementation [15], and no signs of kidney function deterioration were observed in healthy subjects.

Since creatine is an amino acid, it has been suggested that oral creatine supplementation may cause renal "stress." It has not been documented that high daily creatine supplements can alter markers representative of renal dysfunction [24-27].

Creatine is spontaneously converted into creatinine [28], and the increase in creatinine levels in the tissues of subjects who have introduced creatine supplementation will inevitably increase serum creatinine levels, suggesting false renal dysfunction [29].

Thus, creatine supplementation can alter serum creatinine levels and may contribute as a false indicator of kidney injury [30]. Recent studies on novel renal biomarkers [31] and sophisticated statistical investigations [32] confirm that creatine supplementation is safe.

Despite this, today, after more than twenty years of research that demonstrates no adverse effects from recommended dosages of creatine supplements on kidney health, this concern persists [33].

We believe that the patient we observed had a casual finding of an increase in creatinine levels induced by the exogenous intake of creatine without involvement of renal function.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the literature provides evidence that creatine supplementation should be used in the recommended dosage and that those with an existing kidney disease should refrain from using it [14,15]. We also underline the need to pay attention to the use of oral creatine supplements, which are freely available in shops with unattested purity formulations.

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